

**PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS AND ANALYSIS OF
CURRENT PROBLEMS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN**

Omonova Mukhlisa Dusnazar kizi

Alfaragan University

Department of "Pedagogy and Psychology",

Associate Professor, Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical (PhD)

muxlisa.alfraganus@gmail.com

Sotvoldiev Shokhrusbek Nigmatulla oglu

Alfaragan University

Master's student in the field of "Pedagogy and Psychology"

Training future teachers is one of the central directions of educational reforms today. Within the framework of the educational policy pursued in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the formation of a modern teacher personality, improving the quality of education, and training competitive personnel are set as priority tasks. However, it cannot be denied that the systemic problems that remain in the higher pedagogical education system are a serious obstacle to preparing future teachers for modern professional activities.

Since 2017, radical reforms have been gradually being carried out in the education system of our republic. These reforms mainly include priority areas such as improving the quality of education, training competitive and modern-thinking personnel, applying international experience, and introducing advanced technologies. Within the framework of the "Improving the Quality of Education" program adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025, large-scale work is being carried out to increase the efficiency of pedagogical personnel training, introduce innovative educational technologies, and develop the teacher-student tradition. As an actual example of these innovative activities, the following series of innovations can be cited:

Changes in educational programs - recently, educational programs and subject modules have been revised and a number of changes are being made. Competency-based approaches are of particular importance in updating programs.

- Introduction of digital technologies - in order to improve the quality of education and facilitate the provision of education, electronic learning platforms, tests, assignments, distance learning systems are being introduced.

- The existence of a policy to support young personnel. In this, issues related to the education, employment, professional adaptation, and professional development of young personnel are considered as the main idea.

- International cooperation - that is, providing education based on advanced pedagogical foreign experiences in the field of education, providing students with knowledge based on foreign experiences, as well as the organization of joint educational programs with foreign universities.

However, it is worth noting that, along with the existing positive achievements, a number of problems are also emerging in practical activities:

- The lack of coordination of theory and practice is characterized by the fact that although students are given theoretical knowledge in depth during the pedagogical activity, the student is not able to quickly apply his knowledge to practical activities. That is, the student is not fully prepared for the real teaching process.

- Educational and methodological support - some textbooks and manuals do not meet the requirements of modern education, and the provision of new textbooks is not the same everywhere.

- Inadequate quality of personnel - in some cases, the shortage of personnel is a problem, while in others the quality of modern personnel does not meet the requirements. In particular, the low level of knowledge of modern educational methods, the low level of skills in mastering STEAM, 4K, CLIL technologies.

- Insufficient establishment of the teacher-student system - the lack of systematic arrangement of attaching young personnel to experienced teachers in the pedagogical education process. This will inevitably have an impact on education quality indicators.

We make the following recommendations for the current problems in the analysis process:

- Expanding the practice-oriented education system. Creating opportunities for students to actively participate in the real lesson process by integrating the stages of pedagogical practice with the school.

- Improving curricula. Textbooks and methodological materials should be redeveloped based on modern pedagogical technologies and international competency-based approaches.

- Increasing digital literacy. Special courses and training should be organized so that students who want to become teachers can effectively use modern information and communication technologies.

- Strengthening the motivational environment. In order to increase students' internal confidence and interest in the pedagogical profession, it is necessary to expand the incentive system, professional psychological training and social support programs.

- Strengthening the teacher-student system. Qualified and experienced teachers should be assigned as mentors for each student, and a system of regular monitoring and guidance on professional development should be introduced.

- Social appreciation of pedagogical activity. Social packages, benefits, and support systems should be developed to increase the prestige of the teaching profession, encourage young professionals, and retain them in the school system.

The issue of professional training of future teachers in the education system of Uzbekistan is one of the important factors of national development and social stability. The educational reforms carried out in recent years have yielded certain results in terms of strengthening the theoretical knowledge of future teachers, preparing them for practical work, and teaching based on innovative approaches. However, a number of problems remain in the existing system that need to be resolved. In particular, the incomplete compliance of curricula with modern requirements, insufficient practical training, poor skills in working with digital technologies, and a weak motivational and moral-psychological environment - all of these are obstacles to the professional formation of future teachers. Modern education requires teachers not only knowledge, but also such competencies as innovation, freedom of thought, initiative, and empathy. Therefore, not only theoretical, but also practical and motivational approaches are important in the training of future teachers. Improving the quality of education can be achieved by comprehensively solving existing problems in the system.

List of used literature

1. Ministry of Public Education. Concept of Pedagogical Education. Tashkent, 2022.
2. Joraev A. “Fundamentals of Pedagogical Skills and Professional Training”. Tashkent, 2020.
3. Turdaliyev Kh. Quality of Education: Systematic Approach and Perspective. – Tashkent: Science, 2020. – 136 p.